

Energy-aware placement of network functions in edge-based infrastructures with Open Source MANO and Kubernetes

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Abstract. The virtualization of network functions aims to replace traditional network functions running on proprietary middleboxes with software instances running on general-purpose virtualization solutions, looking for more flexible, scalable and sustainable networks. However, despite the availability of platforms and technologies that enable its realisation, there are still technical challenges that have to be addressed to obtain those benefits. One of the challenges is the efficient placement of network functions, considering, for instance, the energy footprint among other constraints and available resources. This paper proposes an energy-aware virtual network function placement and resource-allocation solution for heterogeneous edge infrastructures that considers the computation and communication delays according to the virtual network functions' location in the infrastructure. The solution has been integrated with the ETSI-sponsored project Open Source Management and Orchestration (OSM) as an extension that allows the configuration of virtual network functions and their subsequent resource allocation and deployment at the edge, minimizing energy consumption and ensuring the quality of service. Applied to the deployment of augmented reality services in different scenarios, the results show up to a 51% reduction in energy consumption compared to the default OSM placement and quality of service compliance in all scenarios considered.

Keywords: Edge Computing · energy efficiency · B5G · VNF placement · Open Source Mano · Feature Models

1 Introduction

The execution of traditional network functions (NFs) on proprietary middleboxes has several drawbacks, mainly in terms of high capital, operating and maintenance costs, long deployment cycle, high energy consumption (EC) and the need for expert personnel to manage and configure the plethora of existing equipment. The replacement of traditional network functions running in middleboxes by software instances running on general-purpose virtualization solutions leads to more flexible, scalable and sustainable networks. Network Function Virtualization

(NFV) also meets the evolution in networking required by modern technologies such as Beyond 5G (B5G) and the Internet of Things (IoT), which are looking for more flexible, scalable and sustainable networks. However, although it is widely recognized that NFV solutions need to run as efficiently as possible to address sustainability concerns, existing NFV solutions and enabling virtualization technologies focus mainly on legacy network performance metrics, such as ensuring service availability and neglecting in some way the energy footprint. The efficient realization of NFV poses new challenges to enabling virtualization technologies and NFV platforms solutions [12] to guarantee network performance, NFs dynamic instantiation, their efficient placement and energy footprint reduction.

This paper presents an energy-aware approach for the optimal placement of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs). Our solution is integrated with the Open Source Management and Orchestration (OSM) platform, which provides a VNF manager, and NFV orchestrator and supports connection to third-party Virtualized Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) (e.g., OpenStack). In addition, OSM supports container technology (via Kubernetes [3]) to enable the design and implementation of Kubernetes-based Network Functions (KNFs) [14] running inside containers. Our solution, named HADES, extends OSM by enabling the optimal placement and configuration of VNFs/KNFs and their subsequent resource allocation and deployment at the edge, minimizing EC and ensuring the quality of service (QoS). To this end, Hades provides an energy-aware scheduler for the open-source Kubernetes container orchestrator which assigns VNFs to nodes taking into account the energy consumption (EC), the computation and the communication delay within an NFV infrastructure. The solution has been integrated as an extension of the project [14] and tested in real (not simulated) scenarios of the deployment of typical augmented reality (AR) services (implemented as KNFs). Using a physical energy meter, the EC of the HADES placement solutions are compared with the default OSM placement scheduler. Furthermore, the QoS obtained with both deployments is tested. The results show up to a 51% reduction in EC and QoS compliance in all scenarios considered.

The remainder of this document is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the related work and exposes the limitations of existing VNF placement approaches. Section 3 presents HADES and its integration with OSM, while Section 4 details the different modules that make up our proposal. Section 5 applies our proposal to the deployment of an augmented reality application on a physical edge infrastructure and evaluates the reduction in the EC obtained. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and presents future work.

2 Related work

Both industry and academia have devoted much attention to the development of NFV and edge computing [13].

In the industry, there are several NFV solutions for the management and orchestration of VNF, both proprietary and open source. Concerning open source solutions, on which we will focus in this paper, the most widely used options are OSM (Open Source MANO) [14], Open Platform for NFV (OPNFV, now

mixed with CNIT-Cloud Infrastructure Telco Taskforce) as a new solution called Anuket) [6], and ONAP (Open Network Automation Platform) [4]. Although all of them are very similar, they differ in the amount of resources required for their operation. A deep comparison of installation and operation requirements shows that OPNFV [6] and ONAP [4] require more vCPUs (virtual Central Processing Unit), RAM (Random Access Memory) and disk than OSM, which has a minimum requirement of 2 vCPUs, 6 GB of RAM and 40 GB of disk [14]. This makes OSM the best candidate to integrate with our approach, as the aim of this work is to minimize the EC of VNF deployments in edge infrastructures.

Released in 2016, OSM is primarily developed in Python and runs on Linux operating systems. OSM uses three functional blocks (NFVO, VNFM and VIM) of the NFV MANO to perform VNF configuration and abstraction, and infrastructure orchestration and management. Some of the operations natively supported by OSM are: (i) orchestration service for VNFs; (ii) the possibility of performing complex services; (iii) management of infrastructures with several VIMs associated; (iv) software-defined network (SDN) controllers; (v) monitoring tools. The OSM proposes an open-source implementation of the ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute) NFV architecture publicly available.

Intending to minimize the EC, in [15] authors formulate the VNF placement problem as a decision tree search. The parameters considered during the process are the nodes' CPU, their type and the bandwidth of the links. In [15], the amount of CPU required by the VNFs is fixed, which weakens the applicability of the proposal in heterogeneous infrastructures. With the same objective, authors in [7] propose an NFV scheduling heuristic algorithm to map and schedule traffic flows. Neither [15] nor [7] allows to adapt the nodes in which energy reduction is prioritised according to the needs of the infrastructure.

The work in [16] proposes a Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC)-based VNF placement and scheduling scheme for AR applications, whose objective is to improve the QoS. It deploys AR applications in a simulated environment, regardless of the dependency on peripherals or sensor units. Furthermore, both the cloud and the edge are considered as a set of homogeneous nodes, which simplifies the problem of deciding whether to run the VNFs on the edge, on the cloud or to reject the request. The work in [11] presents a VNF placement model to minimize the end-to-end delays, which is solved using Integer Linear Programming (ILP) and a heuristic algorithm. In [8], authors address the VNF-PC satisfying the delay constraints and reducing the consumption of network resources. The Service Function Chain (SFC, an ordered sequence of VNFs and subsequent steering of flows through them to provide end-to-end services) placement is solved as a Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) and a heuristic algorithm is proposed based on the relaxation and delay check. However, the models presented in these works only consider CPU and bandwidth, while other aspects such as disk or RAM are considered. Considering peripherals within the proposal itself (as ours does) and not only in the deployment descriptors allows not only to take into account their presence but also their characteristics (e.g., GPU frequency) to provide solutions that ensure QoS.

Fig. 1: General overview of our approach.

3 Our approach

Figure 1 shows the integration of our platform HADES with Open Source MANO [14]. HADES is a platform that makes use of OSM and Kubernetes functionality for managing VNFs and KNFs deployments, automating and optimizing the deployment process in order to minimize EC. HADES is composed of two main parts: the Web-based back-end module that provides the main functionalities of HADES; and the front-end control panel, which provides the administrator with a GUI to control, monitor and consult the functions of the back-end. Using the control panel the administrator can initiate the deployment by selecting the VNF/KNF and the configuration of their characteristics. The administrator can also modify and remove existing deployments at runtime. The monitoring module displays the status of the infrastructure resources in real-time. Each module is explained in more detail in Section 4. To carry out these processes, HADES collects and uses information of the infrastructure provided by the OSM API, while it generates and sends OSM-understandable deployment files to OSM (see Figure 1). Specifically, HADES endows OSM with the following capabilities:

- *Minimization of energy consumption of the deployments.*
- *Generation of application configuration*, allowing the infrastructure manager to select both application and QoS-related features before deployment.
- *QoS assurance of the deployments.*
- *Resource allocation optimization*, establishing a minimum and maximum range of resource usage to ensure QoS while minimizing resource waste.
- *Deployments considering multiple VIMs* (not natively supported by OSM).
- *Easy modification of deployments, keeping unmodified application parts intact.*

4 HADES platform

This section presents the operation of the HADES platform and its integration with the rest of the OSM components shown in Figure 1.

4.1 Deployment creation module

The infrastructure manager first selects the VNF/KNF to be deployed from the catalogue to which OSM has access. Then, uses the application feature model (FM) to configure it. Commonly used in software product lines, FMs represent, in terms of features, which elements of a family of software products are common, which are variable and the relationships between them. FMs are represented as a set of hierarchically ordered features, composed of parent-child relationships and a set of constraints which represent the relationships among features. The number

of VNFs/KNFs (or tasks) that form the application and their characteristics will depend on the configuration of the application FM. Once configured, the resulting application (formed by a set of VNFs/KNFs) is sent to the iTAREA module (described later), which returns the most energy-efficient assignment of VNFs/KNFs to nodes and the allocation of resources that satisfies the functional and non-functional requirements of the application. Finally, this solution is used to create deployment files, understandable by OSM, with the optimized deployment of the application. As introduced in Section 3, HADES allows considering the entire infrastructure (i.e., several clusters), as well as excluding specific nodes or clusters from the solution.

Once the deployment is done, the location information of each task is stored to assure the correct communication between VNFs/KNFs. If the location of a task changes, this information is updated. This mode of operation is based on the Mediator design pattern [9].

Efficient Task and Resource Allocator (iTAREA) The efficient Task and Resource Allocator (iTAREA) module is responsible for deciding where should be executed each VNF/KNF and the amount of RAM (Mb), disk (Mb), bandwidth, and percentage of CPU to allocate to each of them. This module is based on the concept that some nodes are more energy efficient than others.

Energy consumption and latency models: The iTAREA uses the following expressions to calculate the latency of the application execution (left) and EC (right), to minimize EC while ensuring the QoS [13]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 tCompu_{i,n} &= \frac{w_i}{CPU_n v_{i,n}} & eCompu_{i,n} &= (1 - \alpha_n)(eMax_n v_{i,n} + eIdle_n) tCompu_{i,n} e w_n \\
 tComm_{i,j,n,z,ct} &= \frac{c_{i,j} + c_{i,j} pR}{Min(R_{n,ct}^{Tx}, R_{z,ct}^{Rx})} + t_{n,z}^{prop} & eIdle_n &= \alpha_n eMax_n \\
 & & eSend_{c_{i,j},n,z,ct} &= x_{i,n} h_{i,j} P_{n,ct}^{Tx} \frac{c_{i,j} + c_{i,j} pR}{Min(R_{n,ct}^{Tx}, R_{z,ct}^{Rx})} e w_n \\
 & & eRecp_{c_{i,j},n,z,ct} &= x_{j,z} h_{i,j} P_{z,ct}^{Rx} \frac{c_{i,j} + c_{i,j} pR}{Min(R_{n,ct}^{Rx}, R_{z,ct}^{Tx})} e w_z
 \end{aligned}$$

where the computation time of task i in node n ($tCompu_{i,n}$) is obtained by the ratio between the number of CPU cycles (w_i , collected using tools like Linux *perf*) required by task i and the CPU frequency of the node per core (F_n) multiplied by the percentage of CPU allocated to the task on the node ($v_{i,n}$). Meanwhile, the communication time is calculated by the ratio between the amount of data to transmit between tasks i and j ($c_{i,j}$)—being pR the probability of retransmission due to packet loss—and the transmission/reception speed (using connection type ct , e.g., *WiFi 2.4, 4G*). The propagation delay $t_{n,z}^{prop}$ is set as the half of the mean round trip time (RTT) obtained by pinging from n to z , and considered like constant [13].

EC (right side of the above equation) at the nodes is influenced by several factors, such as CPU, storage and RAM usage, being the CPU the most influential factor and the most commonly used in the literature [13]. $eCompu_{i,n}$ calculates the computational EC (J) required by the node n to compute task i , while $eIdle_n$ represents the idle EC of a node. The energy consumed by task i to communicate with task j is calculated in the third and fourth expressions of the right side of the equation, which calculate the EC for sending and receiving data from node n to z [13]. Concretely, $eMax_n$ is the EC of node n when it is fully-utilized (in

terms of CPU); v the CPU utilization ratio (from 0 to number of node cores); and α , whose value is between 0 and 1, represents the fraction of the idle EC (e.g., 60%) [13]. This model is based on the observation that the EC is linear to the CPU utilization ratio which depends on the computation load [13,15]. The second and third expressions of the right-hand side of the above equation denote the EC for data sending and receiving respectively from node n to z [13]. P^{Tx} and P^{Rx} represent the transmission powers, while R^{Tx} and R^{Rx} denote the transmission rates for data transmitting and receiving. $x_{i,n}$ is 1 if task i is assigned to node n , 0 otherwise; $h_{i,j}$ is 0 if tasks i and j are assigned to the same node, 1 otherwise. The variable ew (energy weight), whose value is between 1 and 0, represents the importance of energy saving in each node. The higher its value, the more important it is to save energy at that node. This allows customizing the importance of energy savings according to the needs of the infrastructure, unlike other approaches [13]. An example of practical use is to prioritize the assignment in devices powered by solar panels, thus reducing the carbon footprint.

Implementation:

As the CPU depends on the computing capacity of the node, the variable $CPUPartitions$ contains the portions of CPU that can be assigned to each task by each core; this reduces the search range (and therefore the problem complexity). Therefore, if this variable has a value of 10, the CPU will be allocated in portions of 0.1 cores (100 millicores). Concerning QoS assurance, applications have sets of tasks with time constraints (i.e., they must be completed within a maximum time), which are part of the problem constraints.

This module receives as input the information of the nodes (set N), the tasks (τ), the nodes to exclude ($nodesToAvoid$), the set of time restrictions (Tr), and the CPU portions ($CPUPartitions$). As an output, it returns the task assignment and the amount of resources that the node must reserve for each assigned task.

$$\begin{aligned}
\textbf{Input:} & \quad N, Tr, \tau, nodesToAvoid, CPUPartitions \\
\textbf{Minimize:} & \quad energy \rightarrow \forall (n, m) \in N, i \in \tau : x_{i,n} eCompu(i, n) + \\
& \quad \sum_{j \in \tau} (h_{i,j} eSend(c_{i,j}, n) + x_{j,m} eRecp(c_{i,j}, m)) \\
\textbf{Subject to:} & \quad N = N \setminus nodesToAvoid \quad (1) \\
& \quad \forall i \in \tau : \sum_{n \in N} x_{i,n} = 1 \quad (2) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N : \sum_{i \in \tau} x_{i,n} i_{RAM} \leq n_{RAM} \quad (3) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N : \sum_{i \in \tau} x_{i,n} i_{disk} \leq n_{disk} \quad (4) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N : \sum_{i \in \tau} x_{i,n} i_{bandwidth} \leq n_{bandwidth} \quad (5) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N, i \in \tau : x_{i,n} RAM_{i,n} \geq i_{RAM} x_{i,n} \quad (6) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N, i \in \tau : x_{i,n} disk_{i,n} \geq i_{disk} x_{i,n} \quad (7) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N, i \in \tau : x_{i,n} bandwidth_n \geq i_{bandwidth} \quad (8) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N : \sum_{i \in \tau} x_{i,n} CPU_{i,n} \leq CPUPartitionsCores_n \quad (9) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N, i \in \tau : CPU_{i,n} \in \mathbb{N} \quad (10) \\
& \quad \forall n \in N, i \in \tau : x_{i,n} \wedge meets(n, i) \vee \neg x_{i,n} \quad (11) \\
& \quad \forall tr \in Tr, (n, m) \in N, i \in \tau : x_{i,n} tCompu(i, n) + \\
& \quad \quad \sum_{(j) \in tr} h_{i,j} x_{j,m} tCommu(c_{i,j}, n, m) \leq time_{tr} \quad (12) \\
\textbf{Return:} & \quad \forall i \in \tau, n \in N : x_{i,n} \rightarrow RAM_{i,n}; x_{i,n} \rightarrow disk_{i,n}; \\
& \quad x_{i,n} \rightarrow bandwidth_{i,n}; x_{i,n} \rightarrow CPU_{i,n}
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The iTAREA module, formalized in Equation 1, does the following: first, it excludes the nodes to be avoided from the set N (1); (2) checks that each task has a node assigned; (3-5) ensure that nodes have RAM, disk and bandwidth enough to execute their assigned tasks, while (6-8) assure to assign enough resources to properly execute each task; (9-10) check that nodes do not allocate more CPU than available (limiting the search range according to the *CPUPartitions* variable); (11) checks that the nodes fulfil the task requirements (in terms of peripherals and sensing units); (12) verifies the fulfilment of the time restrictions, considering execution and communication times; finally, the iTAREA returns the solution (task assignment, RAM, disk, bandwidth and CPU assigned to each task). To implement the iTAREA module we use the *Gurobi Parallel Mixed Integer Programming* solver. Thus, (1) the algorithm always returns a solution (differently from heuristic algorithms), which guarantees that the deployment is feasible or the impossibility to deploy the application if no solution is found; while both SMT (Satisfiability Modulo Theories) solvers and MILP (Mixed Integer Linear Programming) allow handling the variables required by the problem at hand (unlike others), MILP solvers return the solution faster than SMT solvers [17]; and (3) Gurobi supports multi-threading, which aids problem scalability. Nevertheless, it could be possible to use other solutions to our approach.

4.2 Resource monitoring

This module tracks the status of the infrastructure. Its functions include checking the number of VIMs, their characteristics and their associated cluster (if any); and obtaining real-time information about the node's workload (CPU, RAM, disk and bandwidth). Its functions are mainly two: (1) provides the iTAREA module with the necessary information about the infrastructure to perform its function; and (2) allows HADES to be aware of the most demanded nodes, or of those that should be excluded from some deployments. Regarding its implementation, it is a process that periodically makes requests to the Kubernetes clusters to know their status in real-time. This information is stored at the backend, which keeps a log that could be used for different purposes (e.g., to apply auto-scaling).

4.3 Runtime deployment modification and elimination

This module allows both deleting and modifying existing deployments. The elimination of deployments causes the application to stop running and the nodes to release the resources allocated to its execution. For its part, the modification of deployments allows extending, reducing or modifying the functionality of the applications, keeping intact those parts of the application that are not involved.

Deletion is a relatively simple process: the infrastructure manager selects a deployment from among the active ones and orders to delete it, while, the amount of available resources for each node is updated. Application modifications are carried out using the application FMs. The VNFs/KNFs whose functionality has been modified are deleted and the new VNFs/KNFs are deployed instead. Sometimes, it is not necessary to remove existing tasks, and new tasks are added. The resulting SFC remain connected following the location log maintained at the backend.

Fig. 2: Experimentation setup (left) and SFC of PlanetARium (right)

5 Proof of concept

In this section, we apply our proposal to the deployment of a distributed application based on KNFs.

5.1 Infrastructure

Figure 2 (left) shows the edge infrastructure used. It consists of eleven heterogeneous nodes, a manager and the other ten distributed in three Kubernetes clusters (that use Microk8s (v1.23), a lightened version of Kubernetes to reduce EC and improve the applicability of the proposal). The manager node (Node 1) contains instances of HADES, OSM (its most up-to-date release, ELEVEN), the application repository and three virtualized VIMs (virtualized using OSM’s native *emu-vim tool*). This node runs Ubuntu 20.04 LTS and has 2 cores of CPU (4.2 GHz) and 8 Gb of memory. Cluster 1 has four nodes: a Raspberry Pi 4 (Node 2) running Ubuntu Mate 20.04.1 (4 cores of up to 1.5 GHz, 4 Gb of RAM) as the master node (which is also a worker) and three worker nodes. Node 3 (desktop) runs Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, having 4 cores of CPU (3.10 GHz) and 12 GB of RAM. Node 4 (laptop) runs Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, and has 4 cores of CPU (2.30 GHz) and 4 GB of RAM. Node 5 (Raspberry Pi 3 B+) runs Ubuntu Server 20.04, 4 cores of CPU (1.4 GHz) and 1 GB of RAM. Cluster 2 is formed by three nodes: Node 6 (Raspberry Pi 4, same configuration as Node 2) operating as master and worker node that manages two worker nodes: Node 7 (desktop) runs Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, has 4 cores of CPU (up to 3.70 GHz) and 12 GB of RAM; and Node 8 (laptop) running Ubuntu 20.04 LTS with 4 cores of CPU (2.20 GHz) and 4 GB of RAM. Finally, Cluster 3 contains three nodes: Node 9 (Raspberry Pi 4, the same configuration as Nodes 2-6) operating as master and worker; Node 10 (laptop), with the same configuration as Node 4; and Node 11, a Raspberry Pi 3 B+ (same characteristics as Node 5). Nodes have a clean installation of the operating system, trying to minimize the number of background tasks.

To carry out an efficient task allocation, HADES uses the idle and busy EC of the nodes. Therefore, the EC of the nodes has been analyzed both at idle (with the Microk8s installed) and during a 1-minute CPU matrix stress test. The matrix stressor is a good way to exercise CPU floating-point operations, as well as the memory and data cache of the processor. To measure the EC we use Watts Up? Pro [10], a physical meter that allows real-time monitoring of the amount of energy supplied to the device connected to the power supply.

Regarding communication, the round-trip time between nodes is obtained by pinging from node a to b (considering the average of sending 1000 small packets).

The transmission rate has been analyzed using *iPerf* [2] (considering the average transmission rate of sending packages during 100 seconds). Finally, the power transmission is given directly from the characteristics of the nodes' network cards.

5.2 Case study: Augmented Reality Services

As case study, we have implemented *PlanetARium*, an application that uses augmented reality (AR) services to display virtual planets, constellations, etc, according to the information obtained from a camera. AR applications are widely used in edge computing approaches, as they are computationally intensive and delay-sensitive, and processing all the information on devices with low computational capacity is prohibitively expensive because it would affect users' expectations in terms of QoS [13].

PlanetARium is composed of several interconnected micro-services, each of them being a KNF of the same SFC (see right side of Figure 2). The desired QoS stipulated by the infrastructure manager in the deployment module is 15 FPS (frames per second). Concretely, the KNFs that form the SFC are the following:

- **Video capturer (KNF 1)**: captures video from a camera (required) and adapts the resolution to the one selected by the infrastructure manager.
- **Feature Communicator (KNF 2)**: receives the video stream and converts it to black-and-white video for easy element detection.
- **Filter Selector (KNF 3)**: applies a filter to reduce the brightness of the received video and a blur, assimilating the image to a night sky.
- **Planet Tracker (ArUco Detector, KNF 4)**: searches for ArUco codes in the received video, identifying each one and determining its coordinates.
- **Galaxy Tracker (QR Detector, KNF 5)**: searches for QR codes in the received video, obtaining their coordinates.
- **Visualizer (KNF 6)**: receives the processed video stream and the coordinates of planets and galaxies and overlays the corresponding virtual elements, creating a server accessible through a browser.

All tasks run as Docker containers and communicate through sockets. For video capture and element detection, PlanetARium uses the open source tool OpenCV [5] for Python 3, while for 3D element rendering NodeJS and Three JS. Concerning their requirements in terms of RAM and disk, they are obtained by using the Linux command *htop* and Docker Stats [1]. To assure the desired QoS, we extract the computational cost and amount of data to transmit for one iteration of each task. Then, knowing the time it takes for the deployment to perform a complete iteration (i.e. to execute each task once), we calculate the maximal time per iteration (15 iterations per second in our case, 0.067 seconds per iteration as maximum). Our model uses the number of CPU cycles to determine the computational load of the VNFs/KNFs (see Section 4.1). Using the Linux tool *perf* and a traffic sniffer, we launch 2000 iterations of each task (using different inputs) for each node and establish an average number of CPU cycles and an average amount of data transmitted to avoid the bias that could exist by considering only one type of input for each task. PlanetARium KNFs do not reserve or limit node bandwidth.

Table 1: HADES deployment of PlanetARium

	KNF 1	KNF 2	KNF 3	KNF 4	KNF 5	KNF 6
Scenario 1	Node	2	5	5	4	2
	CPU limits (m)	400-500	400-500	600-700	1400-1500	1200-1300
	RAM limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52
	REC ^a	45.4%				
Scenario 2	Node	6	6	8	8	6
	CPU limits (m)	400-500	300-400	200-300	1400-1500	1200-1300
	RAM limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52
	REC	46.7%				
Scenario 3	Node	9	11	11	10	9
	CPU limits (m)	400-500	400-500	600-700	1400-1500	1200-1300
	RAM limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52
	REC	The OSM deployment does not meet the QoS				
Scenario 4	Node	2	2	2	8	6
	CPU limits (m)	400-500	300-400	400-500	1400-1500	1200-1300
	RAM limits (Mb)	32-42	53-63	42-52	53-63	42-52
	REC	49.6% / 51%				

Fig. 3: Task assignment (left), Table 1 (upper right corner), and energy consumption for the different scenarios (lower right corner)

5.3 Experiments on energy saving

This section compares the EC of the default Kubernetes deployment with that of HADES for the infrastructure and application presented in Sections 5.1 and 5.2. We will consider the deployment of PlanetARium in four scenarios: in Cluster 1, in Cluster 2, in Cluster 3, and in the complete infrastructure (Clusters 1-3). In Scenarios 1-3 we will use both the default Kubernetes scheduler (kube-scheduler) and HADES, while in the fourth one we will perform the deployment only with HADES (OSM only allows to consider one cluster). Finally, we will measure the EC of the nodes before and after deploying the application, thus obtaining the deployment EC. To check compliance with the minimum FPS set at 15, we introduce an on-screen frame counter. For a fair comparison of results, all tests were performed at the same location and on the same day, under the same temperature conditions and node status.

Left side of Figure 3 shows the resulting KNF assignments:

Scenario 1 (Cluster 1): The base consumption (before the application deployment) of Cluster 1 is 77.9 W, being 92.2 W after the PlanetARium deployment. Therefore, the application EC with kube-scheduler is 14.3 W. When deployed with HADES, the EC after the deployment drops to 85.7 W, which means an application EC of 7.8 W. Regarding QoS, both deployments meet the non-functional requirement of 15 FPS. To achieve this, it is crucial to allocate the correct amount of resources to each KNF. Lines 2-5 of Table 1 (upper right corner of Figure 3) contain the resource allocation of HADES for Scenario 1. Kubernetes does not set a maximum resource usage margin (so QoS cannot be assured as deployments increase), as HADES does. Note that HADES assigns KNF 1, which requires a camera, to Node 2 because the Node 2 camera supports video capture at 15 FPS (the minimal QoS desired); the same check would be performed for any other peripheral that could compromise the QoS.

Scenario 2 (Cluster 2): The base EC of this cluster is 76.9 W, increasing to 91.6 W after the deployment using kube-scheduler (see left side of Figure 3). Thus, the application EC is 14.7 W. As for deployment with HADES, the

EC is 84.8 W, resulting in an application EC of 7.9 W. Concerning QoS, both deployments meet the QoS of 15 FPS established in the configuration phase. Lines 6-9 of Table 1 show the HADES resource allocation.

Scenario 3 (Cluster 3): The base EC of Cluster 3 is 14.9 W, which increases to 20.7 W with the default OSM deployment, giving an application EC of 5.8 W. With HADES, the EC after deployment is 22.6 W, which is an application EC of 7.7 W (1.9 W over the default OSM deployment). Nonetheless, the comparison between the two deployments is not fair, as the Kubernetes deployment does not meet the expected QoS; FPS fluctuate between 3 and 11. This is because Kubernetes assigned the most CPU demanding task (KNF 4, right side of Figure 2) to the least CPU powerful node (Node 11, see the left side of Figure 3), causing a bottleneck. On the other hand, the HADES deployment meets the expected QoS (resource allocation is shown in lines 10-13 of Table 1).

Scenario 4 (Clusters 1-3): Considering all clusters, the infrastructure has a base EC of 169,7 W, which rises to 176,9 W after the deployment of PlanetARium. Consequently, the application consumes 7.2 W. Concerning QoS, the HADES deployment meets the expected frame rate of 15 FPS; lines 14-17 of Table 1 contain the resource allocation in the case of HADES.

Lower right corner of Figure 3 collects the EC obtained for the different scenarios. Experiments reveal that the HADES' deployments have reduced the EC compared with kube-scheduler in all the scenarios considered for the same QoS (Scenarios 1,2 and 4). Specifically, in Scenario 1 HADES has obtained a reduction in EC of 6,4 W, which means a decrease of 45.4%. For Scenario 2, the EC reduction obtained was 6 W (46.7%). Applied to Scenario 4, HADES has obtained a reduction of 7.2 W, being the most energy-efficient deployment. This represents a 49.6% reduction in EC compared to deployment using kube-scheduler in Scenario 1, and a 51% for Scenario 2—the scenarios in which the frame rate with kube-scheduler is as desired. Likewise, has been proved that the allocation of resources made by HADES has fulfilled the minimum QoS of 15 FPS established in all cases, while the deployment of kube-scheduler in Scenario 3 has not.

6 Conclusions and future work

NFV and edge computing have established themselves as the key technologies in the adoption of B5G communication technology. Nevertheless, there are still technical challenges to be addressed such as guaranteeing network performance, efficient placement and energy footprint reduction.

This paper presents HADES, a solution developed to work in conjunction with OSM. The result is a platform that optimizes the assignment of VNFs and resources to minimize energy consumption, addressing the problem of NF chaining considering factors typically ignored as disk, RAM or peripherals [12], while assuring the QoS. HADES consists of different modules that allow the creation, modification and elimination of VNFs deployments in edge infrastructures, and resource monitoring. Our proposal has been applied to the deployment of AR services on a heterogeneous edge infrastructure, obtaining a reduction of up to 51% in the EC compared with the default deployment proposed by OSM. QoS

has been measured after deployment, demonstrating that the deployment of HADES met the desired QoS.

In future work, we will work on automating the collection of data needed for deployment optimization by HADES.

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